

Deliverable N°: 8.6
Deliverable Title: Project website
WP N°: 8
WP Leader: LCI
WP Title: Dissemination, exploitation, clustering, and engagement
Delivery Date: 31/10/2023
Actual Date: 31/10/2023
Lead Beneficiary: SPES/Federalimentare
Contributing Beneficiary (ies): LCI, IDENER
Dissemination level: PU - Public (according to the GA)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1	25/10/2023	SPES/Federalimentare	Giorgia Sabbatini
2	26/10/2023	IDENER	María González-Moya
3	26/10/2023	SPES/Federalimentare	Giorgia Sabbatini

SUMMARY

This document constitutes the *Deliverable 8.6 “Project website”* and it aims to introduce the structure of **NOVAFOODIES website** (www.novafoodies.eu), developed with WordPress. Deliverable D8.6 is under responsibility of SPES/Federalimentare, as part of WP8 which is led by LCI.

The present report outlines the structure of the main dissemination channel of NOVAFOODIES. In fact, the official website will be used by the Consortium throughout Project duration to share communication & dissemination activities and maximize their impact.

To ensure a unified NOVAFOODIES identity across platforms, the project has a **visual identity set** consisting of the project logo, colors, templates, and font. This guarantees that the Project's image is easily identified and remembered by users and stakeholders. In addition, all pictures shown on the website are of marine/freshwater environment, to let users easily understand the focus of the Project.

Project general information, promo materials, social media links, official newsletters, public deliverables and events & conferences details will all be available in specific sections of the public website, with the final goal of engaging as many stakeholders as possible, keeping them updated, while sharing results achieved by NOVAFOODIES Partnership.

To best achieve this result, **NOVAFOODIES website** has been conceived in a very appealing and user-friendly way, through the following sections:

- Home page
- Partners
- News & Events
- Media Corner
- Contact Us

INDEX

<i>Document history</i>	2
SUMMARY	3
1	STRUCTURE
.....	5
1.1. Home	5
1.2. About Us	9
1.3. Partners	10
1.4. News & Events	11
1.5. Media Corner	12
1.6. Contact Us	13
2	WEBSITE TRAFFIC MONITORING & ANALYTICS
.....	14
<i>Conclusion</i>	15

1. STRUCTURE

The layout of the website is highly user-friendly: the contents are and will be organised in specific sections, some of which will grow as time goes by and thanks to the inputs of each partner involved in the activity, contributing to give the website a well-organised and uncluttered design.

In the home page, users will find a general presentation of NOVAFOODIES, with General Objectives, as well as the following sections and subsections, organised in the main drop-down menu:

- About Us → Our Background + Our Strategy
- Partners
- News & Events
- Media Corner → Promo Material + Deliverables + Video Library
- Contact Us

1.1. Home

The home page is intended to convey to the audience right away that the project is looking marine and freshwater raw materials (particularly through the logo, its pay-off, and the imagery picked for the header and those used throughout pages), with a focus on innovative functional food production systems for more sustainable value chains.

IMAGE 1 - SCREENSHOT OF THE HOME PAGE OF NOVAFOODIES WEBSITE.

Moreover, scrolling down in the Home Page, users can easily get access to NOVAFOODIES *General Objectives*. As depicted here after, the colors used are in line with those of Project logo, to create visual continuity; the same reason is behind the icon above each square: taking up the waves of the logo, while emphasizing the Consortium’s scope of work, the use of marine and freshwater resources.

IMAGE 2 - SCREENSHOT OF GENERAL OBJECTIVES IN THE HOME PAGE OF NOVAFOODIES WEBSITE.

Continuing down in the home page, after the *General Objectives*, users can find an action button allowing them to discover *Specific Objectives & Actions*.

IMAGE 3 - INTERACTIVE BUTTON TO BE REDIRECTED TO "SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES & ACTIONS".

Again, in the *Home Page* – that, as already specified, is the page where stakeholders can find first but detailed information about NOVAFOODIES – are also present two previews of two other sections: *Our Background* and *Partners*.

IMAGE 4 - SCREENSHOT FROM NOVAFOODIES HOME PAGE: "OUR BACKGROUND" AND "PARTNERS".

In addition, in the *Home page*, before the footer, there is a brief overview focusing on one of the Project's main topics of study of NOVAFOODIES, namely algae.

Algae are proven to be food of great quality and nutritional value for humans, while its production contributes to mitigating climate change by CO2 capture. Micro and macroalgae production have commonly been focused on a narrow range of species, and existing systems are still not technologically efficient. However, algae alone cannot be the entire solution for a more sustainable seafood value chains, which need changes along the entire value chain, controlling of environmental impacts, and diversified production with levels of environmental sustainability and product traceability generating greater consumers' trust.

IMAGE 5 - FOCUS ON ALGAE, IN THE HOME PAGE OF NOVAFOODIES WEBSITE.

Finally, the footer of the website – which is the same throughout it – is conceived to highlight the source of NOVAFOODIES funding, that is to say European Union under Horizon Europe Program, specifying also the Grant Agreement Number, the Privacy Policy, Contact Us quick button, and social media (SM) interactive icons.

IMAGE 6 - NOVAFOODIES WEBSITE FOOTER.

1.2. About Us

The section *About Us* is meant to deeply describe why NOVAFOODIES partnership decided to start working together: demonstrating innovative functional food productions systems based on a more sustainable value chains of marine and freshwater raw materials for conscientious EU consumers. This is thoroughly described in the subsection *Our Background*, in which are explained the new approaches that NOVAFOODIES Consortium will develop. Besides, visiting the subsection *Our Strategy*, that can be accessed through *About Us*, users can understand how NOVAFOODIES partnership wants to achieve targeted results and main objectives.

OUR BACKGROUND

The diversity of species exploited, and products derived from aquaculture and fisheries has remained static in recent decades, driving pressures on environment, including poor feed conversion ratios and coastal eutrophication. Considering the growing population, a **holistic and ecosystems-based restructuring of primary processes and value chains** is a priority in order to achieve more balanced, and efficient aquatic food production systems. In this view, **increasing waste recycling, balancing production** to host environment carrying and regeneration capacities, and **diversifying species production** to better match local conditions should be considered to improve the current situation and boost innovation in this sector. One of the main sources, both directly as (ingredients for) new food products and as the basis to produce other aqua food products are **algae**.

Algae are proven to be food of great quality and nutritional value for humans, while its production contributes to mitigating climate change by CO2 capture. Micro and macroalgae production have commonly been focused on a narrow range of species, and existing systems are still not technologically efficient. However, algae alone cannot be the entire solution for a more sustainable seafood value chains, which need changes along the entire value chain, **controlling of environmental impacts, and diversified production with levels of environmental sustainability and product traceability generating greater consumers' trust**.

Aware of these challenges but often working in isolation, there are many organizations developing solutions to improve efficiency in the aquatic food sector. **NOVAFOODIES** brings together some of these organizations in a unique consortium to demonstrate new approaches that ensure future seafood production is both profitable and environmentally.

OUR STRATEGY

NOVAFOODIES is an interdisciplinary project bringing together partners from **Europe, Israel and China**, with complementary backgrounds to interact closely in a synergistic manner to deliver the expected results, research outputs and **six key objectives**. **NOVAFOODIES** aims to provide consumers with **new functional and traceable products of marine and freshwater origin**, produced with more sustainable processes without compromising sectoral competitiveness.

Specific Objectives & Actions

#01

Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) with 7 case studies in Europe, Israel, and China. IMTA is acknowledged as a promising solution to improve the sustainability and efficiency of aquaculture, as it ensures that wastes and by-products are valorized.

#02

Cultivation of macroalgae in earthen ponds and in liquid wastes for obtaining high-value products, demonstrating the microalgal commercial potential as a novel protein source, while promoting novel products for human consumption.

#03

Microwave-assisted algae drying, bacterial-based algae-decomposition process, extraction of functional components from fish and valorization of fisheries discards for improving the nutritious value of human food products.

#04

Environmental, economic and logistics optimization of processes, and traceability systems implementation to collect and monitor aquaculture data.

#05

Development of NOVAFOODIES marketplace platform and App for end-users.

IMAGE 7 - SCREENSHOT OF "OUR BACKGROUND", "OUR STRATEGY" AND "SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES & ACTIONS".

1.3. Partners

This section is designed to introduce NOVAFOODIES Partners, giving an intuitive overview of their geographic distribution and their profiles (ONG, RTOs, SMEs, Associations, University, Large Companies, Associated and Non-associated Countries).

PARTNERS

IMAGE 8 - NOVAFOODIES PARTNERS MAP.

Users can discover more about each partner scrolling down the page: in fact, under the Partners Map, logos of each entity participating in the Consortium is going to be listed with Country of belonging, and with a hyperlink heading to respective websites. Under evaluation with the website master is the possibility to add below each logo a very brief description of the Partner.

1.4. News & Events

News & Events is meant to be one of the most dynamic sections of the website, as it is going to grow and be animated as time goes by, with the contribution of all partners, in order to let stakeholders be regularly updated about NOVAFOODIES recent developments. SPES/Federalimentare will be in charge to upload materials on the website. This section is divided into two subsections:

- *News* – where users can find out updates about the progress of the project or NOVAFOODIES Program and other articles dealing with relevant and related topics.
- *Events* – where forthcoming public or private events are going to be regularly listed, such as kick-off meeting one which is already available online.

In the main section, users can just have a look at the first lines of the article and by clicking on READ MORE they will be redirected to the full version of the article. Beside the article preview, an image (such as Project logo or other related pictures) will always be shown. In addition to this, most news will be also promoted on SM official channels of NOVAFOODIES Project.

NEWS & EVENTS

🕒 October 10, 2023

Categories ▾

NOVAFOODIES kick-off meeting in Seville!

NOVAFOODIES kick-off meeting took place in Sevilla last 18-19th May. The Consortium met for the first time to officially start NOVAFOODIES activities and to finetune the [...]

[Read more](#)

IMAGE 9 – NEWS & EVENTS PREVIEW.

1.5. Media Corner

As the previous one, also *Media Corner* section of NOVAFOODIES website will be a very active one. It is made up of three different subsections, that is to say:

- Promo Material
- Video Library
- Deliverables.

In the first one, *Promo Material*, all NOVAFOODIES promotional tools will be available for users:

MEDIA CORNER

Promo Material

Video Library

Deliverables

logo, leaflet, poster, roll-up, and newsletter can then be downloaded in PDF format by interested stakeholders.

In *Video Library*, videos recorded at different Project stage will be available, as well as the final Project video, showing all results achieved by NOVAFOODIES consortium.

Last but not least, the *Deliverables* subsection is the space where users will find all NOVAFOODIES Deliverables listed in the Grant Agreement of the Project.

IMAGE 10 - MEDIA CORNER DROP-DOWN MENU.

1.6. Contact Us

The last section of the website is dedicated to show users the NOVAFOODIES Coordinator (IDENER - Spain) and how visitors can get in contact with NOVAFOODIES by using the Project e-mail info@novafoodies.eu.

Besides, on the right part of the page, icons with hyperlinks to NOVAFOODIES Social media account are listed (X, and LinkedIn). These two platforms will be periodically updated with latest news about NOVAFOODIES and related topics.

In this section, interested stakeholders have also the possibility to sign up to NOVAFOODIES newsletter. By subscribing here, users will also receive most important updates about events and news of NOVAFOODIES. The subscription is very easy: it is just needed to add Name, Surname, Company name and E-mail address, not forgetting to read the *Privacy Policy* and tick the related box.

Finally, NOVAFOODIES website is in line with the GDPR 679/2016, which came into force on May 25, 2018. In fact, as already mentioned, it includes a *Privacy Policy* section to let users get informed about how NOVAFOODIES partnership is going to use personal data, how it protects visitors' information, which kind of cookies are used, how modifying information already provided, Third Party Disclosures, Disclosure and Retention of personal information, Services Provided.

IMAGE 11 - SCREENSHOT OF CONTACT US SECTION OF NOVAFOODIES WEBSITE.

2. WEBSITE TRAFFIC MONITORING & ANALYTICS

In order to monitor the advancements and progress of the website, thus verifying the effective achievement of the main objective of creating the website, which is to raise awareness of the NOVAFOODIES project and maximize communication activities, regular checks every 4 months on the website metrics will be carried out by SPES. A specific tool of WordPress will be used to generate analytics and examine main areas of interests, such as:

- Type of sessions visited;
- Users and page views;
- Users' activity;
- Visitors countries of origin.

Metrics and graphs to show the trend of the website will be automatically generated by the program used; they will also be used in Project Reports to show website's efficiency. Looking at the traffic will also be very important to improve, if necessary, the strategy set to communicate NOVAFOODIES results and disseminate its achievements.

As KPIs, the Consortium expects to involve 2.000 users during the period of activity. In the unlikely event that SPES notices a low development of the website, which risks not to reach the desired objective, SPES, with the help of all partners will put into practice even more robust strategies to spread NOVAFOODIES brand, insisting on promoting the website more on NOVAFOODIES Social Media, especially Twitter (as it seems being more suitable for communication purposes of EU Projects).

IMAGE 12 - EXAMPLE OF GRAPHS GENERATED FROM MONITORING NOVAFOODIES WEBSITE METRICS.

CONCLUSION

NOVAFOODIES website – hosted at the URL www.novafoodies.eu and developed with WordPress – plays an important part in the success of the Project, as it is the primary entry point for stakeholders interested in the Project. That is why it has been conceived to be extremely clear and easy to navigate: in fact, NOVAFOODIES website provides visitors with a first and at the same time thorough overview of Project activities and its Consortium.

As it is the main tool for communication & dissemination activities, the website will constantly be updated with news related to Project events, developments, milestones achieved, and other articles that would be of interest for the target audience, in order to raise awareness over topics covered by NOVAFOODIES European Project. In conclusion, the website will be used by NOVAFOODIES Consortium members to maximize the impact of actions, activities and news related with the Project.

This deliverable reflects only the author's view. The Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.